

Ir0000014 – Itserr

Detailed Organisational Plan (DOP)

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Associate project to RESILIENCE RI

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00.02	28/11/2022	DRAFT	Complete revision of the document after ITSERR Board review
01.00	01/12/2022	FINAL	Finalisation
01.01	1/4/2023	FINAL	Change some staff names

Distribution List

Name	Company	Role
ITSERR Board Members	All ITSERR partners	

This document is available in the ITSERR WP Management document repository at:
ITSERR-WP1\o5_Deliverables\D1.1_DOP\

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1 Document overview

1.1 Objectives

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (ITSERR¹) for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

This document is the Detailed Organisation Plan (DOP) for the Grant and represents the reference document by which ITSERR demonstrates that it:

- understands the WPs, its characteristics, peculiarities, risks, innovations, and unknowns,
- has selected the most appropriate WP organisations, techniques, resources, and tools to cope with the above,
- has defined the deliverables, quality assurance, and approval responsibilities and processes and defined the extent and format of checks and reviews,
- has identified the major risks and the corresponding preventive actions.

The major purposes of this DOP are:

- To define the organisational structures that govern the GA;
- Describe the processes, instruments necessary for the proper governance of the GA;
- To ensure MUR about the respect of the GA procedures;
- To define roles and responsibilities, with emphasis on the required skill sets, to address the complexities and risks of the GA,
- To make visible all the means that are applied at governance level to meet the MUR GA requirements,
- To ensure that the GA governance requirements are fully understood by ITSERR,
- To state all the participants of the WP, procedures, rules, and applicable methods.

1.2 Scope

This Detailed Organisational Plan covers exclusively the GA organisational bodies:

ITSERR

as defined in the Grant Agreement number IR00000014 - ITSERR (see applicable document [A2]).

This DOP is to be applied by each staff employed on the WP and to all work performed within it. It is a binding document being part of the contractual documents. In case of misinterpretation or conflicts, the Grant Agreement Contract and its annexes have precedence over this document.

¹ ITSERR is a consortium composed of National Research Council (CNR), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE), Università di Napoli L'Orientale (UNIOR), University of Palermo (UNIPA) and Università degli Studi di Torino (UNITO).

1.3 Applicable documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[A1]	09/08/2022	ATTO D'OBBLIGO CONNESSO ALL'ACCETTAZIONE DEL FINANZIAMENTO CONCESSO PER IL PROGETTO "ITSERR - Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE" - CUP B53C22001770006
[A2]		GRANT AGREEMENT, NUMBER — ??? — ITSERR,
[A3]	To be released soon	Data Management Plan

All documents mentioned in this list are available in the Document Repository, section "Applicable Documents".

1.4 Reference documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[R1]	25/11/2022	Detailed Organisational Plan

1.5 Acronyms

A list of acronyms frequently used in this document.

Term	Definition
CO	Collaborator of a PI (Principal Investigator)
FO	Financial Officer
GA	Grant Agreement
IAB	International Advisory Board
IB	ITSERR Board
IB members	General Assembly
IM	Infrastructure Manager
ITSERR	Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE
MUR	Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca
OU	Organisational Unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PI	Principal Investigator
PLA	Performance Level Agreement
PRC	Peer Review Committee
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SSF	Stakeholders Strategic Forum
TNA	Trans-National Access
VA	Virtual Access

2 Presentation of the Grant Agreement

2.1 Definition of the objectives

ITSERR is based on the postulate that the Humanities can offer superdiverse datasets whose complexity challenges technologies and ICT scholars. Therefore, the project aims at transforming the scientific community of Religious Studies from being a mere actor in the implementation of established technologies to the driver of a new match with the new assets of Artificial Intelligence/Big Data/HPC.

The project is implemented to:

- strengthen the RESILIENCE RI in its preparatory phase, through its national institutional dimension, scientific positioning, technical development and public perception;
- support excellence by putting the more qualified scholars and researchers in Religious Studies and ICT at the service of the excellence in research in Religious Studies, producing disruptive innovation for the domain;
- advance efficiency with the improvement of the accessibility to data, facilities and experts belonging to the national context and promoting data FAIRness;
- expand the RI national network of researchers, users and stakeholders, and be able to translate the national experience on other national contexts and at the European level;
- enhance operativity by offering new services and tools that are ready to be accessed by the end of the project and can thus rapidly enable new research scenarios and
- attract scholarship, research and industry to leverage the Italian scientific community of Religious Studies towards a more innovation-oriented research methodology.

2.2 ITSERR partners Organisational Units (OU)

OU	Accr.	Description
OU1	CNR-ISTI	Istituto di Scienza e Tecnologie dell'Informazione A. Faedo, Via Moruzzi 1, 56124, Pisa
OU2	UNIMORE-DESU	Dipartimento di Educazione e Scienze Umane
OU3	UNIMORE-DIEF	Dipartimento di Ingegneria "Enzo Ferrari"
OU4	UNIOR-DAAM	Dipartimento Asia Africa e Mediterraneo, Piazza San Domenico Maggiore 12, 80133 Napoli
OU5	UNIPA-DCS	Dipartimento Culture e Società, Viale delle Scienze ed.15, 98128, Palermo
OU6	UNIPA-DMI	Dipartimento di Matematica e Informatica, via Archirafi 34, 90123 Palermo
OU7	UNIPA-DI	Dipartimento di Ingegneria, Viale delle Scienze, ed. 8, 90128 Palermo
OU8	UNIPA-IUS	Dipartimento di Giurisprudenza
OU9	UNIPA-ARCH	Dipartimento di Architettura

OU10	UNITO-DSS	Dipartimento di Studi Storici, Via Sant’Ottavio 20, 10124, Torino
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2.3 Global contract phasing

The MUR imposes a certain phasing related to the reporting obligations of the ITSERR partners.

“Rendicontazione di intervento: Rendicontazione bimestrale al Servizio centrale per il PNRR da parte della funzione di rendicontazione e controllo dell’Amministrazione centrale titolare di intervento. Tale attività può ricomprendere la rendicontazione delle spese sostenute dai soggetti attuatori e/o la rendicontazione del conseguimento dei milestone e target associati agli interventi di competenza;”

Aside this, the partners have decided to split the execution of the GA in 12 distinct Work Packages (WP). These are:

Table 1 : List of Work Packages

WP	WP Title	Leader	Start month	End month
WP1	Project Management + Impact	OU1	1	30
WP2	RESILIENCE Data Centre Services	OU5	2	29
WP3	T-ReS	OU2	2	29
WP4	DamSym	OU5	2	29
WP5	DIGITAL MAKTABA	OU5	2	29
WP6	YASMINE	OU5	2	29
WP7	REVER	OU2	2	29
WP8	uBIQUity	OU5	2	29
WP9	Taurus	OU10	2	29
WP10	ReTINA	OU4	2	29
WP11	TNA	OU5	2	29
WP12	Data Management Services	OU5	2	29

2.4 Materials and Services supplied by the MUR

To execute and respect the procedures created by MUR under PNRR, they have provided to the ITSERR community the following material:

- The Grant Agreement
- GEA, the project portal of MUR
- Templates for technical and financial reporting

3 Grant Organization

3.1 Organization, Roles and Responsibilities

3.1.1 MUR organization

Role	Name	Phone	Office	Mail
Legal Officer	MAZZOLA Michele	342 8508551	L.go Antonio Ruberti n.1 – Roma	Michele.Mazzola@mu r.gov.it
Project Officer				

All offices are located in L.go Antonio Ruberti n.1 – Roma

3.1.1.1 Legal officer

The Legal Officer of MUR oversees the management of all legal resources (grant agreement, consortium agreement, etc.) activities to provide services satisfying the requirements of MUR.

He is the last escalation step for the management of this contract.

3.1.2 ITSERR – Decision Making Bodies

3.1.2.1 ITSERR Board (IB)

3.1.2.1.1 Objectives

The ITSERR Board (IB) is the supervisory body of the execution of the WP: it coordinates the horizontal as well as the vertical activities of ITSERR to establish and implement the WP and to grant the fulfilment of the expected results and impacts. It is responsible of the governance of the WP and consists of six members, chosen between the members of the BD and is chaired by the a member elected at the first meeting.

The ITSERR Board (IB) oversees:

- Directing the **quality assurance of the WP** and its technical progress;
- **Monitoring the progress** of the WP and the planned activities;
- **Evaluating** intermediate and final **results**;
- Receiving and approving deliverables;
- Supporting and revising the work of the WP leaders;
- Revising the use of the resources for the activities of the WPs;
- Supporting and evaluating the work of the IM.

3.1.2.1.2 Working procedures

3.1.2.1.2.1 Meetings

The IB is thus in charge of the overall monitoring of the WP and is accountable for the progress and the quality of the deliverables.

It **meets at least each quarter** under ordinary conditions.

Extraordinary meetings can be possible only if critical circumstances strictly require them. They can be called at any time upon written request of the ITSERR Board.

The IM will notify an IB meeting:

- Min. 14 calendar days in advance for an ordinary meeting
- Min. 7 calendar days in advance for an extraordinary meeting

The agenda will be submitted to the IB members by the IM min. 7 calendar days in advance for ordinary and extraordinary meeting.

Any member of the IB can add items to the meeting's agenda min. 2 calendar days in advance for ordinary and extraordinary meetings.

Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the Minutes has been accepted or a decision document approved by the defined majority.

3.1.2.1.2.2 Decision making

The IB shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members are present or represented (quorum). If the quorum is not reached, the IM shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the IM's representative shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented.

The IB takes its decision according to a majority-vote process.

3.1.2.1.2.3 Communication

To communicate with the board, the mailing list is **board@itserr.it**.

3.1.2.1.3 Members

The ITSERR Board (IB) is chaired by the IM (IM) unless decided otherwise in a meeting of the General Assembly. The IB is composed by 5 representatives of some partner institution plus the chairman.

Here is the list of the partners' representatives for the IB.

Chairman	
UNIMORE PI	Alberto MELLONI(UNIMORE)
Members of the ITSERR Board	
Scientific Coordinator	Carlo MEGHINI(CNR)
RESILIENCE.EU CEO	Francesca CADEDDU(UNIMORE)
Financial Officer	Alessandro NARDI (CNR)
UNIPA PI	Fabrizio d'AVENIA(UNIPA)
Infrastructure Manager	Michele CARRAGLIA

3.1.2.2 Infrastructure Manager (IM)

3.1.2.2.1 Objectives

As specified in the GA signed by ITSERR partners and communicated to MUR, the ITSERR IM for this contract is an employee of the CNR. The IM leads the Grant Agreement.

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The IM oversees:

- **Coordinating** the development of the whole WP and of the WPs;
- Collecting the periodical reports of the WP leaders;
- Preparing any progress report as well as the Final evaluation report
- Facilitating the activities of the IB;
- Managing the MUR financial contribution;
- **Representing ITSERR** in the effective execution of the formal and informal communication with the MUR.

The IM chairs the ITSERR Board.

3.1.2.2.2 Communication

To communicate with the IM, the mailing list is im@itserr.it.

3.1.2.3 Support Office (SO)

3.1.2.3.1 Objectives

The Support Office (SO) consists of communication, legal, administrative and financial staff from all ITSERR partners. The SO:

- Is co-chaired by the IM and the FO;
- Financial and administrative reporting;
- Collecting the financial and administrative periodical report of each partner;
- Responsible for ordering and contracting material and services needed for the ITSERR project (ie call for tenders for IT services, office renting, ordering consumables, etc.);
- Communication about legal, administrative, financial rules to be respected by all ITSERR entities;

3.1.2.3.2 Working procedures

3.1.2.3.2.1 Meetings

The SO meets bi-weekly or on an ad-hoc basis triggered by specific needs.

3.1.2.3.2.2 Communication

To communicate with the so, the mailing list is so@itserr.it.

3.1.2.3.3 Members

The International Advisory Boards (AIB) consists of members selected within renowned European institutions and universities and representing the institution's technical expertise to the ITSERR project.

3.1.2.4 International Advisory Board (AIB)

3.1.2.4.1 Objectives

The International Advisory Board (AIB) consists of internationally scientific renowned members selected outside the consortium and providing expertise for the various WPs. The AIB:

- Provides expertise on the specialistic deliverables submitted to the IB;
- Works as a meta-board coordinated by the SC;
- Provides technical advices to individual WP;
- Offers feedback to the IB concerning the quality of the activity and identify possible contingencies concerning the strategy followed to reach the ITSERR proposal;

3.1.2.4.2 Meetings

The AIB meets on an ad-hoc basis triggered by specific needs. In the occasion of its first meeting, the SC is nominated chairman.

3.1.2.4.3 Communication

To communicate with the AIB, the mailing list is aib@itserr.it.

3.1.2.5 Members

The International Advisory Boards (AIB) consists of members selected within renowned European institutions and universities and representing the institution's technical expertise to the ITSERR project.

3.1.2.6 Stakeholders Strategic Forum (SSF)

3.1.2.6.1 Objectives

The Stakeholders Strategic Forum (SSF) consists of members from political, academic and cultural institutions supporting the project, interested or potentially interested in it. The SSF:

- receives periodical communications on the progress of the project;
- is invited to major project events.

3.1.2.6.2 Working procedures

1. Meetings

The SSF meets on an ad-hoc basis triggered by specific needs. In the occasion of its first meeting the SSF elects its.

3.1.2.6.3 Communication

To communicate with the SSF, the mailing list is ssf@itserr.it.

3.1.2.7 Members

The International Advisory Boards (SSF) consists of members selected within the consortium and representing each partner's technical expertise to the ITSERR project.

3.1.2.8 Peer Review Committee (PRC)

The Trans-National Access processes will be fully described in the TNA Management Plan (D11.1).

Some discrepancies might appear between the DOP and the TNA-MP. If it is the case, the TNA-MP has precedence over the DOP for the PRC working procedures.

3.1.2.8.1 Objectives

The WP leaders for the associated TNA chairs the activities of the Committee and coordinate its operation, taking care of the documentation of its activities. Their activities are:

- Analyse the list of candidates proposed one month after the TNA call publication
- Rank them according to specific indicators
- Provide a written classification of these WPs to the IM and the IB.

3.1.2.8.2 Working procedures

3.1.2.8.2.1 Meetings

The PRC meets in person or making an appropriate and accurate use of web tools (for instance, Zoom conference) in developing its advisory activity. The Committee meets by one month after the TNA submission deadlines and after each meeting provides a detailed and appropriate report ranking the approved WPs and their classification in order of priority, addressing this document to the PC and the IB.

3.1.2.8.3 Proposals ranking and decision making

- Step 1: qualification

All proposals dossiers are first qualified to ensure that they are relevant to the TNA call for proposal (CfP).

If they are complete and compliant with the CfP, they are submitted to the evaluation of all members.

- Step 2: ranking

The decision process is triggered one month after the CfP publication. Then each member of the PRC submits his/her WP ranking according to the CfP indicators to the chairmen.

The ranking process is the following:

- Each PRC member receives an excel worksheet with a list of indicators. Each indicator should receive a value (0 lowest score – 10 highest score)
- The PRC member evaluates the proposal and score the proposal versus each indicator
- The spreadsheet is filled with the scores and is submitted to the chairmen when completed

Here is a non-exhaustive list of TNA WPs evaluation indicators.

- WPs with a large and deep Italian/European impact;
- WPs having a woman group leader or principal investigator, or the gender balance within the group members is to be fulfilled, or which include specific focus on gender issues;
- WPs led by young scholars who aim to significantly improve their training in humanities and particularly in historical religious studies;
- WPs proposed by users who belong to countries where no research infrastructure or research platform in historical religious studies exists;
- WPs proposed by users who have no previous access to collections resources or to the participant provider's facilities;
- WPs that require a strong integration between the access to special collections and the use of digital tools.

The rankings are always made on the basis of the following criteria:

- Research quality of the proposal;
- Originality of the research activity;
- Level of expertise of the potential user;
- Potential innovation of the research WP.

- Step 3: qualification by the chairmen

The chairmen merged all reports and verifies the score of each proposal.

- If a proposal has a global score superior to 50%, it is qualified.
- The proposals with the highest scores are selected to fill in the number of posts made available within the CfP.
- The chairmen write a report that is communicate to PRC members, the SC and the IB.

Note: Qualified proposals which could not be awarded a post in the relevant facility can be included in the next call for another facility.

- Step 4: mitigation of cases

Some mitigations cases might occur. For example, one remaining post is available and the 2 highest ranking proposals have the same score.

In mitigation cases, a vote will occur. In this case, the voting procedure will be the following:

- The PRC deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its Members have voted;
- If the voting quorum is not reached, the Chairmen shall convene another “session” within 5 calendar days.
- If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the Chairmen shall convene an extraordinary “voting session” which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of Members are present or represented.

The PRC takes its decision according to 2/3 majority-vote process.

3.1.2.8.4 Communication

To communicate with the TNA Leader, the mailing list is tna-l@itserr.it.

To communicate about the TNA, the mailing list is tna@itserr.it.

To communicate with the PRC, the mailing list is prc@itserr.it.

3.1.2.9 Members

The Peer Review Committee (PRC) consists of seven members, one internal and six external, and oversees the scholarly review and ranking of the TNA submissions. The internal member is the WP leader involved with TNA (WP11) while the five external members are international acknowledge experts in the field of historical religious studies selected by the IB with the advice of the IAB in the occasion of its first meeting.

These 5 members and the chair of the PRC will be named after the recruitment of the TNA Manager.

3.1.3 Work Packages (WPs) organisation

The management of ITSERR supports the autonomy of ITSERR Work Packages organisation.

To that respect, ITSERR endorses an Agile approach of the activities supplemented by SCRUM. SCRUM is a lightweight framework that helps people, teams and organizations generate value through adaptive solutions for complex problems.

The diagram below represents a way to organise ITSERR's WPs delivery. Clearly, the teams and their organisation depend on the content of the WP as defined in the Grant Agreement, but in general the ITSERR organisation structure is as shown below.

Figure 1: ITSERR teams organisation

3.1.3.1 Project & Quality Management Team

It is composed of 1) the Infrastructure Manager; 2) the Project Management Office (PMO) including:

- technical Project Manager(s),
- a Security Officer and
- a Test team to validate the product/services increments realised by developers.

The availability of the PMO team will be secured by a Call for Tender (CfT) followed by a contract with an IT service company delivering the PMO services to ITSERR. At the moment of the DOP writing, the MUR has not issued the financial guidelines and CNR/Univisities administrations cannot plan when such a CfT can be launched, the contract and the PMO services started. This is a systemic risk related to the project as a whole.

The PMO team performs the following non-exhaustive list of activities:

- Helps the Support Office in preparing Prepare Specific Work Order and follow-up the ordering process,
- Helps staffing the IT/UX teams and ensure Training Management for all teams,
- Set-up and follow-up of the development/test/operation of the infrastructures,
- Understand and master DevOps tools, techniques and workflow.

3.1.3.2 Support Office team (SO)

The team is composed of:

- **Members of the administrations of CNR and the university partners.** It helps administer the admin tasks necessary for universities, CNR and MUR including legal, financial and administrative aspects;
- **A Communication Manager:** writes down and is responsible for the implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP-D1.3). The plan adapts the C&D strategy of RESILIENCE to ITSERR, guaranteeing a sound coordination on what, how, when and to whom is communicated to the Italian and European targeted audiences. It covers topics such as strategy for online communication, social media collaboration, face-to-face collaboration, conferences and workshops, feedback management, corporate design, tools, channels, touchpoints, monitoring, analytics and reporting;
- **An Impact Manager:** is responsible for measuring the technical and socio-economilca impact of the ITSERR project and creating the Impact Analysis report(IAR-D1.4). The document reports on the metrics and indicators as understood within the RESILIENCE impact measurement context and measure them according to the RESILIENCE impact areas.

More information on the working procedures of the SO can be found at section 3.1.2.3.

3.1.3.3 Cross-WP Organisation

Is organised by a team accountable for ensuring that all cross-functional and interoperable work is produced. It ensures that standards and best practices of RESILIENCE are applied adequately.

Figure 2 : Work Packages Organization

3.1.3.4 WP Leader (WP-L)

Each WP is organised as presented in Figure 2. The WP Leader is a Researcher responsible for the research activities of the WP. S.He leads the research team and reports to the Scientific Coordinator (SC) and the Infrastructure Manager (IM).

In coordination with the Infrastructure Manager (IM) of ITSERR, the WP leader participates to the WP management and defined at project start, a generic and high-level Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)² (high-level realisation agenda), and leads the WP realisation.

The responsibilities of the WP Leader are, apart from performing general project management, to perform quality assessment of the deliverables before their submission for acceptance to the ITSERR Board and later on to MUR.

WP Leader's responsibilities include:

- informing the IM about WP status including work progress, risks, utilization of resources, Key Performance Indicator, etc.
- examining and discussing with the Scientific Coordinator(SC), the Product Owner (PO), UX Lead (UX-L) and the IT Lead (IT-L) matters of individual tasks in development and their interfaces with another WP,
- performing quality audits related to Best Practice usage and quality conformity related to the Quality Assessment Plan,
- reading and verifying content-related conformity of received deliverables against GA assumptions,
- verifying the correction of deliverables' issues discovered by reviews performed by IB/MUR before formally (re)submitting the deliverable for acceptance to IB/MUR,
- informing the Task Leaders about development of new topics or changes in the existing WP deliverables.
- Being the point of contact of the IM for all issues related to the specific WP

One or more members of the WP team assist in generating the draft and final version of the deliverables.

3.1.3.5 Product Owner (PO)

By using SCRUM, the WP deliveries will be **iterative** and **incremental**.

1. Research team co-creates (researches) solutions to a complex problem and validate/test it with the UX Lead
2. Product Owner, "orders" the work to the IT Team through a WP Product Backlog.
3. IT Team turns a selection of the work (Sprint Backlog) into an Increment of value during a Sprint(max. duration=1 month).
4. At the end of the sprint, the WP Team and its stakeholders inspect the results, verify that it matches the quality criteria³ and adjust for the next Sprint.
5. This is repeated until the product goal, aka the WP objectives, is achieved.

² In effect, the WP Teams will iteratively use Sprints to increment the value of the WP product until it meets the WP objectives. Sprints enable predictability by ensuring inspection and adaptation of progress toward a Product Goal at least every calendar month. Therefore a WBS is not an adapted instrument to an Agile management of the WP.

³ In SCRUM, an increment has produced the expected delivery when the Sprint increment of product value meets the Definition of Done(DoD). The **Definition of Done**, defined collectively by the WP-L and POs, is a formal description of the state of the Increment when it meets the quality measures required for the product.

In this context, the Product Owner is reporting to the WP-L and is accountable for maximizing the value of the product resulting from the work of the team. How this is done may vary across WP, organizations, teams, and individuals.

The Product Owner is also accountable for effective Product Backlog management, which includes:

- Developing and explicitly communicating the Product Goal;
- Creating and clearly communicating Product Backlog items. The Product Backlog is an emergent, ordered list of what is needed to improve the product. It is the single source of work undertaken by the Team. Product Backlog items that can be Done by the Team within one Sprint are deemed "Ready for Selection" (RfS) in a Sprint Planning event;
- Ordering Product Backlog items and,
- Ensuring that the Product Backlog is transparent, visible and understood.

The Product Owner may do the above work or may delegate the responsibility to others. Regardless, the Product Owner remains accountable.

For Product Owners to succeed, the entire organization must respect their decisions. These decisions are visible in the content and ordering of the Product Backlog, and through the inspectable Increment at the Sprint Review.

The Product Owner is one person, not a committee. The Product Owner may represent the needs of many stakeholders in the Product Backlog. Those wanting to change the Product Backlog can do so by trying to convince the Product Owner.

3.1.3.6 User eXperience Lead (UX-L)

The WP Leader is assisted by a User eXperience researcher (UX Lead) which supports the Research team to collect properly the requirements and co-create solutions to complex problems and validate/test them. S.He will be assisted by different UX profiles and reports to the WP Leader.

The availability of the UX Services team will be secured by a Call for Tender (CfT) followed by a contract with a UX service company delivering the services to ITSERR. At the moment of the DOP writing, the MUR has not issued the financial guidelines and CNR/Univisities administrations cannot plan when such a CfT can be launched, the contract and the PMO services started. This is a systemic risk related to the project as a whole.

3.1.3.7 IT Lead (IT-L)

The IT Lead will support the research team in evaluating the IT feasibility of the envisaged solutions. S.He reports to the WP Leader.

3.1.3.8 Research Team

Is composed of RTDs and PHDs plus the academics or non-academics experts needed to address the scientific challenges of the project. Theyr report to the WP Leader.

3.1.3.9 IT Team

Is composed of the necessary IT profiles working as a SCRUM Team and allowing the architecture, design, implementation, testing and set in operation of the artefacts to be produced monthly within each sprint and each sprint being iterated monthly until the end of ITSERR.

The availability of the IT Services team will be secured by a Call for Tender (CfT) followed by a contract with a IT service company delivering the services to ITSERR. At the moment of the DOP writing, the MUR has not issued the financial guidelines and CNR/Univisities administrations cannot plan when such a CfT can be launched, the contract and the PMO services started. This is a systemic risk related to the project as a whole.

3.2 Staffing

3.2.1 Work Package Leaders

Here is the list of the Work Package leaders.

Work Package	First Name	LAST NAME	Acronym	Organisation
WP1	Rudy	DEMO	DER	OU1
WP2	Fabrizio	D'Avenia	DAF	OU5
WP3	Alberto	MELLONI	MEA	OU2
WP4	Fabrizio	D'Avenia	DAF	OU5
WP5	Fabrizio	D'Avenia	DAF	OU5
WP6	Fabrizio	D'Avenia	DAF	OU5
WP7	Alberto	MELLONI	MEA	OU2
WP8	Fabrizio	D'Avenia	DAF	OU5
WP9	Stefano	Di Martino	DIS	OU10
WP10	Andrea	D'Andrea	DAA	OU4
WP11	Fabrizio	D'Avenia	DAF	OU5
WP12	Fabrizio	D'Avenia	DAF	OU5

Table 2 : Work Package Leaders

3.2.2 Products Owners

Here is the list of the Product Owner(s) per Work Package.

Work Package	First Name	LAST NAME	Acronym
WP3	Federico	ALPI	ALF
WP4	Costanza Marianna	BIANCHI NAPOLITANO	BIC NAM
WP5	Federico Riccardo	RUOZZI MARTOGLIA	RUF MAR
WP6	Federico	RUOZZI	RUF
WP7	Anna	MAMBELLI	MAA
WP8	Laura	RIGHI	RIL
WP9	Stefano	Di Martino	DIS
WP10	Andrea	D'Andrea	DAA

Table 2 : Product Owners

3.2.3 Support Office Members

Here is the list of members of the Support Office.

Organisation	Name	Role(s)
CNR	NARDI Alessandro	Amministrazione
CNR	DEMO Rudy	IM
UNIMORE	CAEDDU Francesca	IB
UNIMORE	REBECCHI Barbara	Amministrazione
UNIMORE	LOMI Maria Giulia	Amministrazione
UNIMORE	BEDIN Elisa	Amministrazione
UNIOR	FLAMINIO Gabriele	Amministrazione
UNIOR	D'ANDREA Andrea	PI
UNIOR	MANZO Andrea	PI/CO
UNIOR	TOTTOLI Roberto	Rettore
UNIPA	TROPEA Luciano	Amministrazione
UNIPA	SCALISI Patrizia Marcella	Amministrazione
UNITO	CINI Monica	Amministrazione
UNITO	CUNIBERTI Gianluca	Direttore dip
UNITO	DE MARTINO Stefano	PI
UNITO	GEUNA Stefano	Rettore
RESILIENCE	PARRELLA Maria	Amministrazione
RESILIENCE	IAROCCI Irene	Amministrazione/Segreteria
ALL	New Joiners recruited for ITSERR admin tasks	

3.2.4 Other roles

At the moment of the writing, the call for Applications for the following roles were submitted but not yet staffed.

- **Communication Manager:** is recruited for the project and will start around 02/2023
- **Impact Manager:** is recruited for the project and will start around 02/2023

4 Work Packages Planning and Effort

At the moment of the writing, the WP Leaders are working to refine the WP description of the proposal. Therefore the following information will be adapted following the progress of this requirements analysis and solution design activities.

4.1 Overview

RESILIENCE.ITA will follow state of the art IT standards, methodologies, tools and processes.

As for RESILIENCE.EU, we will use **Design Thinking** and **Agile/Scrum** as core approaches as there are in Italy a large pool of such trained experts. Scrum is well suited for its agility, fast developments of new developments as well as evolutive maintenance for such a research-based projects.

To **respect EU and Italian accessibility directives**, our teams will also endorse usability and accessibility standards such as accessibility standards (i.e. WCAG 2.1, ATAG, UAAG and XAG, etc.).

For **ensuring security-proofed development and operations**, we complement our approach with **DevSecOps** to: i) allow the deployment of code faster and in an automated way; ii) increase speed to delivery of applications and services; iii) ensure alignment of development and IT operations (in the same way that agile aligns development and researchers/users); and iv) integrate security in the design process. Agile DevSecOps is compatible with Continuous Integration (CI) / Continuous Development (CD) principles, ensuring that the software can be reliably released any time. The goal is that, as all project will highly (re-)use common RESILIENCE software components and libraries, that all WP software components are merged into the main development branch as often as possible, passing automated tests before each commit. CI/CD does not replace Acceptance Testing, but quickly provides incremental releases, using as much automation as possible.

For technical documentation, their scope and content are specified by endorsed development standards such as **Rational Unified Process (RUP)**.

4.1.1 Planning

Here are presented the GANTT chart of each individual Work Package based on the data of the proposal.

- WP1

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- ▼ WP1 - Project & Impact Mtg
 - ▶ Management Tasks
 - ▼ Team Tasks
 - ▶ Governance set-up 30/4/25
 - ▶ Monitoring 3/3/25
 - ▶ Finance, Administration and HR Management 30/4/25
 - ▶ Impact Management 19/4/25
 - ▶ Communication Management
 - ▶ Training Management 30/3/25
 - ▶ ITSERR Closure 30/4/25

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● WP2

▼ WP2 - Data Centre Services

List

▼ Team Tasks

■ Data Centre Services (DCS)	30/4/25
■ Technical analysis	16/7/23
■ DCS Services Level Requirements	7/7/23
■ Preparation	15/6/23
■ Reviews and revision	6/7/23
■ Acceptance and publication	16/7/23
■ Planning and ressource allocation	13/8/23
■ Update of the Operations Management Policy (OMP...)	1/3/23
■ Preparation	13/7/23
■ Reviews and revision	3/8/23
■ Acceptance and publication	13/8/23
■ Documentation	12/3/25
■ Data Centre (DC) Operations technical documentati...	12/10/23
■ Preparation	11/9/23
■ Reviews and revision	2/10/23
■ Acceptance and publication	12/10/23
■ Training material for RESILIENCE DC services users	12/3/25
■ Preparation	24/2/25
■ Reviews and revision	31/1/25
■ Acceptance and publication	12/3/25
■ Implementation	30/4/25
■ Test	30/4/25
■ Operation	30/4/25
■ Monitoring of Operation services	20/3/25

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WP3 - T-Res

List

Team Tasks

- T-Res 30/4/25
- Analysis 30/3/25
- Scientific Preparation 30/3/25
- Whitepaper on Toolkit Libraries 27/10/23
- Whitepaper on CRITERION 21/10/24
- Whitepaper on GNORM 21/10/24
- Whitepaper on the results using GNORM on Corpus ... 20/12/24
- Development 28/2/25
- Test 30/3/25
- Operation 29/4/25
- Training Materials for RESILIENCE 18/2/25
- Data publishing (Corpus Iuris Canonici and Talmud ... 18/2/25
- Prepare CRITERION and GNORM for publication to R... 19/4/25

WP3

Associate project to RESILIENCE RI

WP4

WP4 - DaMSym

List

Team Tasks

DaMSym	30/4/25
Development	28/2/25
Analysis	30/3/25
Scientific Preparation	30/3/25
Whitepaper on DaMSym	22/8/24
Whitepaper on the results using DaMSym on Nicene...	21/10/24
Test	30/3/25
Operation	30/4/25
Training material, manual and documentation for RE...	18/2/25
Data publishing (Nicene-Constantinopolitan Symbo...	19/4/25
Prepare DaMSym for publication to RESILIENCE mar...	19/4/25

WP5

WP5 - Digital Maktaba

List

Team Tasks

Digital Maktaba	30/4/25
Prepare DIGITAL MAKTABA for publication to RESILIE...	19/4/25
Training Materials for RESILIENCE	18/2/25
Analysis	30/3/25
Data publishing on RESILIENCE	18/2/25
Scientific Preparation	30/3/25
Whitepaper on new algorithms	26/12/23
Whitepaper on the software DIGITAL MAKTABA	20/12/24
Development	28/2/25
Test	30/3/25
Operation	30/4/25

Associate project to RESILIENCE RI

● WP6

▼ WP6 - Yasmine

☰ List

▼ ☰ Team Tasks

- Yasmine 30/4/25
- Analysis 30/3/25
- Scientific Preparation 30/3/25
- Whitepaper on YASMINE 23/6/24
- Whitepaper on Sanctuaria datasets 21/10/24
- Whitepaper on Plorabunt datasets 21/10/24
- Development 28/2/25
- Test 30/3/25
- Operation 30/4/25
- Training Materials for RESILIENCE 18/2/25
- Data publishing (Sanctuaria and Plorabunt datasets) ... 19/4/25
- Prepare YASMINE for publication to RESILIENCE mar... 19/4/25

Associate project to RESILIENCE RI

• WP7

▼ WP7 - ReVeR

List

▼ Team Tasks

- ReVeR 30/4/25
- Analysis 30/3/25
- Scientific Preparation 30/3/25
- Whitepaper on corpus pre-processing 28/8/23
- Whitepaper on algorithms 22/8/24
- Whitepaper on REVER 21/10/24
- Development 28/2/25
- Test 30/3/25
- Operation 30/4/25
- Training material, manual and documentation for RE... 18/2/25
- Data publishing of new metadata on Requesta Pontifi... 19/4/25
- Prepare REVER for publication to RESILIENCE market... 19/4/25

Associate project to RESILIENCE RI

- WP8

- ▼ WP8 - UbiQuity

- List

- ▼ Team Tasks

■ Ubiquity	30/4/25
■ Analysis	30/3/25
■ Scientific Preparation	30/3/25
■ Whitepaper on algorithms and corpus preparation	27/10/23
■ Whitepaper on uBIQUity	24/2/24
■ Whitepaper on the results using UBIQUITY on Bible a...	21/10/24
■ Development	28/2/25
■ Test	30/3/25
■ Operation	30/4/25
■ Training material, manual and documentation for RE...	18/2/25
■ Publishing of new Bible and Qur'anic commentaries...	19/4/25
■ Prepare uBIQUity for publication to RESILIENCE mar...	19/4/25

- WP9

- WP9 - Taurus
 - List
 - Team Tasks
 - Taurus 30/4/25
 - Analysis 30/3/25
 - Scientific Preparation 30/3/25
 - Whitepaper on EnLil 27/10/23
 - Whitepaper on MiRAR 26/12/23
 - Whitepaper on ACIS 24/2/24
 - Development 28/2/25
 - Test 30/3/25
 - Operation 30/4/25
 - Training Materials for RESILIENCE 21/10/24
 - Data publishing on RESILIENCE - EnLil 20/12/24
 - Data publishing on RESILIENCE - MiRAR 20/12/24
 - Data publishing on RESILIENCE - ACIS 20/12/24
 - Prepare the TAURUS toolkit (EnLil, MiRAR and ACIS) f... 19/4/25

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Associate project to RESILIENCE RI

• WP10

▢ WP10 - Retina

☰ List

☰ Team Tasks

- ReTINA 30/4/25
- Analysis 30/3/25
- Preliminary Data-Model 24/4/24
- Scientific Preparation 30/3/25
- White paper: report on digital archives on ancient rel... 27/10/23
- Preparation 23/9/23
- Reviews and revision 7/10/23
- Acceptance and publication 27/10/23
- Development 28/2/25
- Data-acquisition procedures 23/6/24
- Prototype for Annotation Tools and interactive interf... 21/10/24
- Test 30/3/25
- Operation 30/4/25
- Prepare ReTINA for publication to RESILIENCE RI ma... 19/4/25

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Associate project to RESILIENCE RI

- WP11

- ▼ WP11 - Trans-National Access

- ☰ List

- ▼ Team Tasks

■ Trans-National Access (TNA)	1/4/25
■ TNA Services Brainstorming	Nov 25
■ Preparation Workshop	Nov 6
■ TNA Services Analysis	Nov 21
■ Reviews and revision	Nov 23
■ Analysis of costs and resources available	Nov 24
■ Selection and prioritisation of services to be implem...	Nov 25
■ Planning of TNA activities	12/1/23
■ TNA Management Plan	12/1/23
■ Preparation	Dec 24
■ Reviews and revision	7/1/23
■ Acceptance and publication	12/1/23
■ Execution of TNA activities	30/3/25
■ TNA activities follow-up	1/4/25
■ TNA Management Report	1/4/25
■ Preparation	1/3/25
■ Reviews and revision	22/3/25
■ Acceptance and publication	1/4/25

Associate project to RESILIENCE RI

● WP12

WP12 - Data Management Services	
Team Tasks	
Data Management Services	12/9/23
Preparation	Dec 29
Acceptance and publication	29/1/23
DCS Services Level Requirements	7/7/23
Planning and ressource allocation	13/8/23
Acceptance and publication	12/10/23
Preparation	11/9/23
Data Centre Services (DCS)	30/4/25
Review Workshops	11/8/23
Preparation	15/6/23
Preparation	12/8/23
Data Services Brainstorming	16/8/23
Preparation Workshops	7/6/23
Data Management Services Analysis	6/8/23
Selection and prioritisation of services to be imple...	16/8/23
Data Management Plan	12/9/23
Reviews and revision	2/9/23
Acceptance and publication	12/9/23
Reference Data Management Plan	1/3/23
Reviews and revision	19/1/23
Implementation	30/4/25
Technical analysis	16/7/23
Test	30/4/25
Reviews and revision	6/7/23
Acceptance and publication	16/7/23
Update of the Operations Management Policy (OMP...	1/3/23

■ Preparation	13/7/23
■ Monitoring of Operation services	20/3/25
■ Reviews and revision	3/8/23
■ Acceptance and publication	13/8/23
■ Documentation	12/3/25
■ Data Centre (DC) Operations technical documentati...	12/10/23
■ Reviews and revision	2/10/23
■ Training material for RESILIENCE DC services users	12/3/25
■ Preparation	24/2/25
■ Reviews and revision	31/1/25
■ Acceptance and publication	12/3/25
■ Operation	30/4/25
■ Monthly Status Report	Dec 1
■ Monthly Status Report	Dec 31
■ Monthly Status Report	30/1/23
■ Monthly Status Report	1/3/23
■ Monthly Status Report	31/3/23
■ Monthly Status Report	30/4/23
■ Monthly Status Report	30/5/23
■ Monthly Status Report	29/6/23
■ Monthly Status Report	29/7/23
■ Monthly Status Report	28/8/23
■ Monthly Status Report	27/9/23
■ Monthly Status Report	27/10/23
■ Monthly Status Report	26/11/23
■ Monthly Status Report	26/12/23
■ Monthly Status Report	25/1/24
■ Monthly Status Report	24/2/24
■ Monthly Status Report	25/3/24
■ Monthly Status Report	24/4/24
■ Monthly Status Report	24/5/24

5 Project Communication

A generic purpose of communication in an organisation is that of enabling, or at least facilitating, the execution of its processes.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP-D1.3) adapts the Communication and Dissemination strategy of RESILIENCE to ITSERR, guaranteeing a sound coordination on what, how, when and to whom is communicated to the Italian and European targeted audiences. It covers topics such as strategy for online communication, social media collaboration, face-to-face collaboration, conferences and workshops, feedback management, corporate design, tools, channels, touchpoints, monitoring, analytics and reporting.

Some discrepancies might appear between the DOP and the CDP as the latter is written later. If it is the case, the CDP has precedence over the DOP for the Communication and Dissemination procedures.

The present document covers communication between the different organisational bodies for the global monitoring and execution of the GA.

Other details about communications (*who communicates what, and to whom*) are described in detail below. Please refer to them for the complete information.

Another important aspect of communication is providing MUR stakeholders with a complete and continuous flow of information about the health status of the WP, expressed also as KPIs. This aspect of the communication process is also examined in detail in the Quality Assessment Plan (QAP-D1.2).

5.1 Meeting process

The GA has defined various bodies to execute the GA. This document presents the composition of these bodies and so the participation in the various organisational bodies.

5.1.1 Frequency

The frequency of the meeting is described in Table 3.

5.1.2 Participants

The participants to the meeting is described in Table 3.

5.1.3 Objectives

- Approving the minutes of the previous meetings
- Informing the members about the status of the GA and board's specific actions
- Defining and planning the priorities for the next period(s)
- Monitoring the execution of the board's activities
- Management of risks, including the approval of the residual risk(s)
- Making the necessary decisions affecting the GA/WP, concerning:

- Deliverables
- Milestone results
- Change Requests
- Risks management
- Quality aspects and enhancements

5.1.4 Invitation

Invitations are sent by the chairman of the board according to the predefined and agreed schedule as defined in Table 3. A meeting room (physical/digital) is reserved by the Chairman's secretariat.

The meeting agenda, the eventual report and the minutes of the previous meeting must be provided electronically to the participants at the latest with a pre-defined number of working days before the meeting as specified in Table 3.

5.1.5 Generic Agenda

1. Approval of the previous meeting minutes
2. Review of still opened actions
3. Review of the eventual Continuous Reporting issues and the periodical report if any
4. Quality issues
5. Performance indicator analysis for the past period (presentation of KPI and possible exceptions, identification of systemic issues)
6. Risk review (review existing risk, new risks)
7. Other business points
8. Next meeting
9. Summing up of actions to be registered and conclusion

5.1.6 Reporting and distribution list

The minutes are made by the chairman and uploaded onto the ITSERR Document Repository at the latest x working days after the meeting (see sections 3.1.2).

5.2 Escalation Meeting (on demand)

The escalation meeting is invoked when a representative of a board determines with the IM that an issue requires escalation for resolution. The escalation is called by any party to ensure critical issues are raised soon enough to prevent undesirable impacts to the GA/WP and to ensure the appropriate parties are informed and involved in critical decision-making.

5.2.1 Participants

Any representatives of MUR, ITSERR partners and subcontractors, according to the meeting topic.

5.2.2 Objectives

No predefined specific topic.

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5.2.3 Invitation

As the meeting is not predefined, a formal invitation is necessary. A meeting room (physical/digital) is reserved by the IM.

5.2.4 Agenda

No predefined specific agenda.

5.2.5 Reporting and distribution list

The minutes are made by the ITSERR IM and uploaded onto the Document repository.

5.3 Meetings

5.3.1 Summary table

Meeting	Participants	Purpose	Invitation sent by	Frequency	Report	Note	Document Location ⁴
ITSERR Board meeting	IB members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of the status of the WP • Risk • activity progress • open problems and proposed solutions • KPIs 	IM	Quarterly	Draft minutes	The agenda is submitted 14 working days prior to the planned date	
Steering committee meeting	IM, SC, WP Leaders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of the status of the WP • Planning • activity progress • open problems and proposed solutions • status of work orders • KPIs • resource allocation • submitting a new resource 	IM	Monthly	Draft minutes and Monthly Progress Report (MPR)	The agenda is submitted 3 working days prior to the planned date	
Support Office meeting	IM, SO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial and administrative status; • Presenting financial and administrative periodical data of each partner; • Status of the orders and contracts for material and services needed for the ITSERR project (ie call for tenders for IT services, office renting, ordering consumables, etc.); • Communication about legal, administrative, financial rules to be respected by all ITSERR entities; 	IM/FO	Bi-weekly	Draft minutes	The agenda is submitted 3 working days prior to the planned date	
Stakeholders Strategic Forum	IB,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • strategy for the next year • trend analysis 	IM	Annual	Draft minutes	The agenda is submitted 21	

⁴ Directory of the document in the Document Repository, see Quality Assessment Plan document.

Meeting	Participants	Purpose	Invitation sent by	Frequency	Report	Note	Document Location ⁴
	IM, SSF members, IB guests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> evaluation of the status of the WP 				working days prior to the planned date	
International Advisory Boards meeting	AIB members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview of the status of technical deliverables submissions Status on metadata requests; Status on technical advices to the Peer Review Committee; feedback to the IB concerning the quality of the TNA activity and identify possible contingencies concerning the TNA provision; Advice the IB about the quality and impact of the communication, dissemination and exploitation of the results, helping in identifying the most efficient and effective solutions. 	AIB Chairmen	Semester	Draft minutes	The agenda is submitted 14 working days prior to the planned date	
Team meeting	Each WP Team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> monitoring the level of state of art of the activities/services Open problems and proposal solutions Constant sharing of information regarding current activities. Each staff member exchanges information weekly about any event regarding operational services and staffing (request from MUR, IM, holidays, staff on leave, sickness, etc.) Risks (security and others) 	WP Leader	weekly			
Ad hoc Meeting	Any organisational board, MUR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Particular events Reaction to critical problems Escalation meeting 	IM	On demand	Draft minutes		IM/Ad-hoc Meetings

Table 3: Meetings summary table

In the section hereunder is provided the detailed information about the principal meetings that are mandatory to monitor the performance of ITSERR related to the GA.

5.4 Reporting

5.4.1 Monthly Progress Report (MPR)

The Monthly Progress Report summarises the activities that have been carried out in the previous month and those to be started in the coming period. It shall be complete and accurate, especially in its description of progress and identification of problems and proposed solutions.

This document is internal to ITSERR, made by the IM from the inputs of WP leaders and to be used as part of the bi-monthly Reporting requested by MUR.

This report provides the ITSERR Board with relevant details on ITSERR in a standardized form, updated during the WP Progress meeting. The report is split into two documents, the main document, presenting the most important pieces of information in a synthesized way and an annex containing detailed information.

The main document must include the following sections:

- **Executive Summary section** containing:
 - an overview of the activities executed during the period, WP per WP with major problems
 - a high-level description, for each WP, of the activities planned for the next period; it should contain for each WP the planning of planned releases
 - a list of major quality issues, as well as a short description of any deviation to the KPI
 - a description of new risks proposed to be included in the risk management process
- **Organization chart section:** with detailed and updated information on the organization of the Grant (organization chart with services and nominated staff)
- **WP status section:** presenting the WP execution baseline, for each WP included in the DOP, with updated milestones and delivery dates. It must include the activities achieved in previous periods for each WP, as well as the forecasted activities for next period.
- **Budgetary section:** this section presents eventual budgetary issues and the necessary financial section to report to the MUR.
- **Human resources section** with changes to the human resources used for the Grant Agreement, with name and profile
- **Risks section:** which contains the list of open risks for all services, together with the mitigation actions
- **Continuous Improvement Process section:** (Optionally), presentation of the WP Sprint Retrospective⁵ outcomes conducted during the period.
- **Service Level and Quality section:** this section contains:

⁵ Sprint Retrospective is a way to increase quality and effectiveness. The Team inspects how the last Sprint went with regards to individuals, interactions, processes, tools, and their Definition of Done. Assumptions that led them astray are identified and their origins explored. The Team identifies the most helpful changes to improve its effectiveness. The most impactful improvements are addressed as soon as possible.

- KPI measurements for the period covered for the period covered for all services and the history since the signature of the Grant Agreement;
- Explanations of the deviations from the KPI targets;

6 WP Management

6.1 Progress measurement and monitoring

At the global WP level, the report of the progress measurement is made to the Steering Committee.

The progress measurement and monitoring of the services are made – mainly – through the Weekly Team meeting.

6.2 Information about work progress

The information on the work progress is communicated via the progress reports and via meeting minutes of the different committees (see sections 5.3 and 5.4).

6.3 Issue handling

The WP Leader or the PO is responsible for collecting overall WP-related issues. Each issue must be allocated to an owner and the issues will be followed up in the weekly Monitoring Meeting. If no agreement is found during the Monitoring Meeting and the contract does not clearly address the case, the issue is escalated to the Steering Committee.

6.3.1 The issue escalation

It is part of the responsibilities of each member of the WP to report and/or solve the problems.

In case of conflict or critical problem (impact and priority), the escalation process is bottom-up from the author:

- to the IT-L and/or to the UX-L
- to the WP-L and/or the PO
- and, if further escalation is needed, to the whole Steering Committee.

Each level of escalation has to fix – after discussion – the target date at which the issue must be answered and/or solved before escalation to the next higher level.

Escalation for Urgent matters shall be done directly to each level responsible.

Escalation procedure shall be documented, reported, and followed up until closure.

7 Control of the DOP

7.1 Preparation

DOP should be delivered for 11/2019.

7.2 Follow-up Activities

The DOP is a living document which is updated at least yearly to take account of new information and changed requirements, and whenever it is required by MUR.

This update follows the same MUR acceptance process than the initial version.

The ITSERR IM is in charge to revise and update the DOP as appropriate.

7.3 Lack of Adherence to the DOP

The ITSERR IM is responsible for the follow-up of the DOP prescriptions during the whole GA.

An explicit review of the DOP as well as a measurement of the adherence will be done at least yearly, and the detected deviations and/or potential enhancements will be reported to the ITSERR IM who will assure that all corrective actions are taken.

8 Annex 1 - Glossary

Term	Definition
Baseline	A significant state within the history of any planned activity
Best Practice	Proven Activities or Processes that have been successfully used by multiple Organisations.
Blocking problem	A problem for which no workaround solution is available at the time of the discovery and which prevents the normal use of the product or of a main functionality
Change management	The process responsible of controlling and tracking changes to deliverables.
Change Request (CR)	A general term for any request from a stakeholder to change an artefact or process. A change request can be an Enhancement Requests or a Defect
MUR	Direction Générale de la Recherche
Escalation	Process that pass information and/or requesting action on an incident, problem or change to more senior staff (hierarchical escalation)
Grant Agreement	Contract signed between the Commission and the ITSERR consortium for the provision of research activities for the creation of a community and research infrastructure on religious studies
Incident	An unplanned interruption to a service or a reduction in the quality of a Service.
Information System	A system, whether automated or manual, that comprises people, machines, and/or methods organised to collect, process, transmit, and disseminate data that represent intermediate of final outputs of business processes.
Performance Indicator (PI)	A Metric that is used to help manage a Process, Service or Activity. Many Metrics may be measured, but only the most important of these are defined as PIs and used to actively manage and report on the Process, Service or Activity. PIs should be selected to ensure that Efficiency, Effectiveness, and Cost Effectiveness are all controlled.
Monthly Progress Report (MPR)	Report provided every month containing all necessary information to follow-up the Grant execution
Performance Level Agreement (PLA)	Agreement between ITSERR and the Commission specifying, in measurable terms, the levels of performance to be provided to the Commission.
Continuous Improvement Review (CI)	CI is a comprehensive feedback process designed to assess WP outcomes and performance. This assessment focuses on how well the WP outcomes were matched to the actual needs that the WP aimed to fulfil.
Process	Sequence of activities designed to accomplish a specific objective. A Process takes one or more defined inputs and turns them into defined outputs. A Process defines roles, responsibilities, tasks, tools, standards and management controls required.

Repository	A storage place for work products (artefacts) output during process enactment, such as requirements, results (i.e. metrics), object models, interfaces, and implementations.
Review	Activity carried out to discover potential defects and to assess the quality of a set of artefacts.
Risk	A possible Event that could cause harm or loss or affect the ability to achieve Objectives. A Risk is measured by the probability of a Threat, the Vulnerability of the Asset to that Threat, and the Impact it would have if it occurred.
Risk Management	The Process responsible for identifying, assessing and controlling Risks.
Service	A means of delivering value to Customers by creating Outcomes Customers want to achieve without the ownership of specific Costs and Risks.
Work Package (WP)	Agreement between the MUR and ITSERR to perform a particular set of activities grouper under a common topic or theme. Each WP has a set of activities under a defined schedule and with defined deliverables, effort, and resource constraints.
WP leader	The WP leader is the interface between the IB and WP team members. The WP leader is responsible for ensuring that a task is allocated and monitored to completion. The WP leader is responsible for ensuring that staff follow WP standards, and adhere to WP schedules.

(End of Document)

